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A: LASER BEAM BANNING OF BAND GAP REGIONS OF SI-H SAMPLES

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Abstract: *The article deals with the topic of lasers in higher education physics dedicated to teaching methodology. The structure and operation principles of lasers are used achievements and shortcomings of the fields are described.*

Key words: *Laser, stimulation, spectrum, resonator, metastable, neodymium glass, methodology.*

Nowadays, it is difficult to imagine some types of production without lasers. Laser technology is used by specialists in various fields - technologists, engineers, creators of various equipment, and all researchers working in other fields attracts more. This is one of the great signs of modern times of lasers working on the basis of forced radiation of microparticles creation and their coherent radiation for various purposes in industry laser devices and technological complexes intended for use to its creation. On this day, lasers and laser technologies are used. In particular, various in the microelectronics industry laser cutting, welding and strengthening of materials from light in the field of medicine in diagnosis, treatment of diseases and surgery measurement in the process, as an information transmitter in the communication system, in the field of science and technology and as diagnostic tools, and coherent radiation in the educational process is widely used to demonstrate wave and particle properties. Laser development of the use of lasers due to the development of technology interest in the issues is increasing. This, in turn, was noted above processing and handling of materials using lasers, as mentioned above increases attention to research. It is being processed in the next 20 years creators of heating materials using laser devices and others is increasingly attracting all researchers working in the field.

Let's talk about lasers. The word laser is English derived from the word "laser". The word "Laser" means "Light Amplification by Stimulated Emission of Radiation" is derived from the initials of the phrase "Mandatory Intensification of light due to radiation". Laser radiation electromagnetic waves in the ultraviolet, infrared and visible range. These waves are based on forced (stimulated) radiation of atoms and molecules is generated. A device that generates such radiation is a laser or optical quantum is called a generator (OKG). Soviet physicist V.A. Fabrikant discharged gas in 1940-1941 light "due to forced radiation" during spectrum studies proved that it is possible to increase the intensity. In 1955, Soviet physicists A.M. Prokhorov and N.G. Basov created the first quantum generator of extremely high frequency. This was an optical quantum generator-maser in the microwave range. By 1958 At the same time as Prokhorov and Basov, US physicist Ch. Towns stands out it is possible to build a quantum generator-laser in the range of the light spectrum

they proved it practically.

Laser materials are the working materials used in laser devices are called or they are called active (active) substances. Ruby crystal as an active medium The laser used (ruby) was created in 1960. Later discoveries included neon Ne and helium A laser using a mixture of He gases (1960s), with the addition of neodymium Nd $3+$ ions laser using silicate glass (1961), semiconductor compound calcium-arsenic Laser using CaAs crystals (1962), neodymium solution in inorganic liquid lasers using selenoxychloride SeOCl_2 and organic dye solutions (1966) was created. By 1974, the number of active substances (laser materials) had reached 200. Har Ionic crystals with various impurities form the largest group of laser materials is enough. Laser glasses with a disordered internal structure are glass formers consists of ions obtained as components and active compounds. semiconductor laser materials AII B VII and A III B It consists of crystals with compound V will be. In them, the working element is a p-n junction with a thickness of $0.1 \mu\text{m}$ A $1 \times 1 \times 0.2$ mm plate is made as shown.

So, depending on the active environment, lasers:

- Solid body
- Liquid (chemical)
- Gaseous
- Semiconductor
- Paint substance can be divided into types.

The atomic structure of the active substance is very important in the principle of operation of lasers. In the excited (disturbed) state of the atoms of the environment, in the metastable state or it is necessary to have the characteristic of "staying for a long time" in an agitated state. Atoms are 10^{-7} without any "motivation" depending on the structure -10^{-9} they are in a second metastable state. Simple when light passes through the medium, it is absorbed and its intensity decreases. while in an active environment it is observed that it increases and increases in intensity during the propagation of light. Such environments are active or inverse (reversed) environments in terms of energy levels of particles is called Optical quantum generator (OCG) or laser active medium, exciter. It consists of a (vibrating) device and a resonator. Laser depending on the type of active environment devices are solid, liquid, gas, semiconductor and paint will be in the form of lasers. The environment is disturbed (awakened, agitated) "trigger" using a triggering device is done. In solid-state lasers, the excitation or "optical pressure" is strong performed with the help of light. Gas lasers from an electric discharge (spark). Semiconductor lasers active medium working part through p-n junction it works based on the transfer of the flow of electrons (electric current). Inverse busy environment from resonators (two near transparent mirrors) in increasing the radiation intensity is used. Multiple passage of propagating photons through the active medium is carried out using a resonator. In lasers, they are interceptors and acts as an amplifier. Lasers work in a 3- or 4-level model can be shown. In three-level generators, "laser radiation" is the inverse of electrons based on its location between the level and any of the "awakened" levels,

four-level and in generators, it occurs between two "awakened" levels. Three-level scheme to lasers working with ruby laser. An optical resonator (pulsed light source) is an example. Included in this group lasers made of chromium Cr³⁺, samarium, uranium U, neodymium Nd³⁺ and other elements enters. Up to 0.05% chromium Cr³⁺ in ruby (ruby) laser aluminum with added ions a crystal made of oxide Al₂O₃ is used (Fig. 1). In lasers, the bases are parallel A cylindrical stem is used. The light from the pulse lamp is active creates a vibration in the environment. Do not hesitate to create a laser beam a battery of charged capacitors with up to joules of energy through a lamp discharged. The lamp illuminates the ruby shaft with a light stream for short periods of time. When a strong light stream from a pulsed lamp hits the ruby, chromium ions from the lamp "wake up" by absorbing the green and yellow parts of the emitted radiation spectrum state, i.e. it goes to the third energy level. After a short period of chromium ions, spontaneously passes to the second (metastable) state without radiation. it is ready to radiate creates an active environment. p,n- semiconductor diode. Laser radiation is stimulated by lamp radiation is generated. The radiation power of the laser reaches 2 kW. Its useful work coefficient is 0, 1-10%. Liquid lasers are organic dyes are lasers working in solution. In these lasers, the "optical pressure" is ruby laser or neodymium glass laser performs. In gas lasers, the active medium is pure gas or gases will consist of a mixture. Helium-neon laser is an example of this. The gas mixture is brought to an "awakened" state by an electric discharge. This is a laser the resonator is placed vertically on the axis of the gas tube. This laser beam is $\lambda = 0.633 \mu\text{m}$ is a coherent wave or generates infrared light of $\lambda = 1.15 \mu\text{m}$. Application of lasers in other fields. Laser light energy in space and the possibility of collection in time, the possibility of collection in a certain spectral interval them:

- ❖ Interaction with various substances in pulse and continuous mode increase (laser technology, laser fusion, laser spectroscopy);
- ❖ Selective effect on atoms, molecules, ions and molecular systems photoionization, photochemical reaction, induction in laser chemistry and laser light elements are used in the separation of isotopes.
- ❖ Accuracy of the place where energy is introduced when introducing energy into substances (localization) quantitative accuracy, the purity of the light beam is characteristic of laser light.
- ❖ Lasers are used in technological processes (metal cutting, processing, widely used in welding, melting). It is a gas with great power in these processes lasers are used.
- ❖ Ultrapure metals in metallurgy in vacuum and controlled gas environment allows you to get Solid-state lasers in spot (welding) welding is used.
- ❖ Ultra-short-pulse laser radiation causes rapid changes used in learning and quick photography.
- ❖ Laser is widely used in diagnosis and treatment in medicine. Lasers are effective in eye and skin diseases, bloodless surgical operations is being used. Ultrastable lasers are the basis of the frequency optical standard, laser seismography, gravimeters are the basis of precise physical instruments. By changing the frequency

tunable lasers (dye lasers) are revolutionary in spectroscopy led to change. They enhance the ability to distinguish in spectroscopy, It is the basis for increasing the sensitivity of the methods, and it is even possible to obtain a separate atomic spectrum created (laser spectroscopy, nonlinear spectroscopy, etc.). Laser locators to identify and eliminate pollution in different layers of the atmosphere and It helps to control, determine the rate of impact, atmospheric temperature and composition allows learning. The laser location of the planets is the gravitational constant clarified its importance, brought space navigation to a higher level. Mercury made it possible to measure the rotation speed of the planets and study their surface. Laser location determined the characteristics of the Moon and Venus. Previously obtained astronomical compared with the results and ensured the accuracy of the results. Emergence of laser citing "Nonlinear optics", "Holography" and other departments of physics released. Conducting a controlled fusion reaction using a laser work has been strengthened. A laser (quantum) gyroscope was implemented. Laser beam village in the fight against agricultural pests, in geological research, automatic in management work, automatic control work in industry (counting details), bodies It is widely used in non-damaging control of the surface. Development of laser technology in Uzbekistan. Laser physics and technology

Uzbek scientists have been making a significant contribution to its development. In particular, Nonlinear optics at the Akademasbob scientific production association of UzRFA fundamental research started on; laser in the former Department of Thermal Physics research of new materials needed to create systems and devices to do; Effect of laser beams on the surface of a solid body at the former Institute of Electronics study; Registration of laser radiation at the National University of Uzbekistan, images restoration, development of new methods of holographic data recording and improvement; laser plasma and multi-charged ions at the former Institute of Nuclear Physics many directions, such as the study of the processes that occur in the emission scientific-research and scientific-technological works are being carried out. By scientists the achieved achievements are applied to various branches of the national economy, both material and brings moral benefits. In particular, Tashkent agricultural engineering plant, Tashkent instrumental plant, Tashkent motor plant, Tashkent cable plant and laser technologies of steel materials in similar production organizations cutting and welding, product marking and precision (high precision) necessary for the cable sheath without stopping the processing, production printing of stamps recording information, electronic in electronic industrial enterprises it is used for the purposes of standardizing details and so on. "Lidar".environment in our region by means of a special laser device called cleanliness is controlled; lasers in the hands of a surgeon and a surgeon - an ophthalmologist. Summary. Presentations in the teaching of the topic of lasers, multimedia, a smaller laser on the use of devices, laser pointers and the structure of lasers videos can be used. Explaining their internet sites and it is possible to show. In Russian and English on the fields of application of lasers materials can be brought. These materials are appropriate during the lecture if used, the quality and efficiency of training will increase.

REFERENCES

1. Rakhmatov I.I. Rakhmatova H. Haydarova M. Physics lessons in high school Peculiarities of environmental education in teaching "Current physics its place in modern education". Proceedings of the republican scientific and practical conference. Samarkand. 2019. December 13-14.-B.124-126.
2. Rakhmatova H., Haydarova M. Ecological education and education Urokkah physics and secondary school. International scientific conference "Global science and innovations 2019: Central Asia". Nur-Sultan. Kazakhstan. December 10-12th 2019. pp. 72-741
3. Rakhmatov I.I. Kakhorov S.K., Mukhammedov Sh.M Osobennosti postroenia obrazovatel'nogo protsessa na osnove modularnykh tekhnologiy obucheniya v to Uzbekistan. Vestnik nauki i obrazovaniya #18 (96) Moscow 2020 chast 2, pp. 33-37
4. Rakhmatov I.I., Ismailova I. Independent in the field of physics education organization of work in the credit-module system. Talented students are graduate students republic on the subject of "Thinking and interpretation" of basic doctoral students and doctoral students collection of scientific-practical conference. Bukhara-2021. B. 48-54
5. Rakhmatov I.I. Rakhmatov Sh.I. From electronic dictionaries in physics classes method of use. "The role of physics in modern education". Republic Proceedings of scientific and practical conference. Samarkand. December 13-14, 2019. - B. 28-29
6. Rakhmatov I.I teaching physics in vocational colleges Pedagogical principles of using electronic manuals. Education introduction of innovative ideas and modern technologies in the process the main strategy of education. Materials of the scientific-educational conference of the Republic collection. Bukhara. 2018.-B. 157-159